

INTERFACIAL TENSION AND MOLECULAR INTERACTION

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Interfacial tension measurements indicate molecular interaction through H-bond between *iso*-amyl acetate and chloroform, aniline, methylaniline, methyl salicylate or *iso*-amyl alcohol. Such an interaction is not evident between *iso*-amyl acetate and benzene, nitrobenzene, chlorobenzene, toluene, heptane, carbon tetrachloride or dimethylaniline. It is also observed between *iso*-amyl alcohol and aniline, methylaniline or chloroform, when two liquids are mixed in certain proportions. Palmitic and lauric acids, cetyl alcohol and citronelol indicate the same behaviour as that of *iso*-amyl acetate, when mixed with *iso*-amyl alcohol; so the fatty acid, alcohol or a constituent present in oil lemon should have a H-bond structure as that of *iso*-amyl acetate.

Some alcohols and esters having unstable H-bond structure have been found to show increase in interfacial tension against very dilute soap solutions (*Curr. Sci.*, 1952, 21, 218; this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 209, 283). This anomalous increase in tension is, however, preceded by depression, when still more dilute solutions are employed (*Science & Culture*, 1954, 19, 609; this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 769). The peaks in tension-concentration curves of different salt systems have been attributed to auto complex and complex formations (*Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 15; this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 287, 421, 872; 1954, 31, 163, 329, 415, 418, 633 640; *Science & Culture*, 1953, 18, 259). This phenomenon has been interpreted on the basis of sensitivity of H-bond structure of such liquids to electrical double layer reversal at the interface with change in electrolyte concentration (cf. this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 286; 1954, 31, 636, 769).

The present investigation indicates that this phenomenon is also observed, when such a substance is mixed with different liquids in definite proportions, and further, that such a characteristic mixture can be obtained from two liquids, even though each separately does not show such a behaviour. Explanation for such observations has been attempted on the basis of molecular interaction involving the formation of H-bond between the H-atom of one kind of liquid molecule and donor atom of a different molecule. Few and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 753, 2663, 2781) showed that the molecular polarisation of aniline was much higher in dioxane than in benzene solution, and the difference between the values in the two solvents was found smaller for methylaniline and quite small for dimethylaniline. The high values observed for aniline and methylaniline have been explained on the basis of molecular interaction involving the formation of H-bonds between the amino H-atoms and one of the oxygen atoms of the dioxane molecule. Molecular compound formation has also been shown by means of dielectric polarisation (Earp and Glasstone, *ibid.*, 1935, 1709) in the type $R_2O.CHX_3$, due to the formation of H-bond between haloform hydrogen atom and the oxygen atom of ether. Similar molecular interaction was also observed between haloform and acetone or quinoline, the linkage being O...H for acetone and N...H for quinoline. Hammick *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1938, 1755) found that trimethylamine formed the complex with chloroform most readily, di-*iso*-propyl ether less readily and

nitromethane, not at all, as a result of H-bond formation between the donor atom of the amine or ether and chloroform H-atom. They further suggested that independent methods, besides polarisation measurements, must be used for determining extent of association.

EXPERIMENTAL

Liquids were purified by usual methods. Mixtures of *iso*amyl acetate (5 to 95% by volume) were prepared with *iso*amyl alcohol, chloroform, methyl salicylate, aniline, methylaniline, benzene, chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, toluene, heptane, CCl_4 and dimethylaniline each. Mixtures of *iso*amyl alcohol with chloroform, aniline, methylaniline, cyclohexanone, diphenyl oxide, palmitic and lauric acids, cetyl alcohol, citronelol (Schering Kahlebaum), ethyl cyanoacetate or malonate were also prepared in different proportions. Interfacial tension of these mixtures was measured by the drop volume method against aqueous salt (CdI_2 , HgCl_2 , or CuCl_2) solutions of different concentrations. As the tension-concentration curves of amyl acetate-salt systems indicate depression at $0.05 \times 10^{-3} M$ and two peaks at $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, the drop volumes, instead of tension values, can be also conveniently employed, and so some of the typical results are expressed in Table I.

TABLE I

Liquids indicating peaks at $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ of CdI_2 or CuCl_2 or HgCl_2 solns.

- (1) Amyl acetate.
- (2) Amyl acetate (10%) + CHCl_3 , aniline, methylaniline, methyl salicylate or *iso*amyl alcohol.
- (3) Amyl acetate (60%) + heptane, benzene, chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, toluene, CCl_4 or dimethylaniline.
- (4) *iso*Amyl alcohol (50%) + CHCl_3 , methylaniline or aniline.
- (5) *iso*Amyl alcohol (60%) + CHCl_3 , methylaniline or aniline.
- (6) *iso*Amyl alcohol (50%) + diethyl malonate or ethyl cyanoacetate.
- (7) Citronelol.
- (8) *iso*Amyl alcohol (90%) + citronelol, cetyl alcohol, lauric acid or palmitic acid.

Liquids which do not show such peaks with salt solns.

- (1) Heptane, benzene, chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride or dimethylaniline.
- (2) Chloroform, aniline, methylaniline or *iso*amyl alcohol.
- (3) Amyl acetate (50%) + heptane, benzene, chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, or dimethylaniline.
- (4) *iso*Amyl alcohol (70%) + chloroform, methylaniline or aniline.
- (5) *iso*Amyl alcohol (50%) + diphenyl oxide or cyclohexanone.

The results indicate that mixtures of *iso*amyl alcohol, chloroform, methyl salicylate, aniline and methylaniline, each containing 10% or more of amyl acetate, show the same behaviour as the pure acetate; while those of benzene, chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, toluene, heptane, CCl_4 and dimethylaniline, each containing more than 50% of the acetate, show such a behaviour. Mixtures of *iso*amyl alcohol with

chloroform, aniline or methylaniline 50% each, behave similarly, though each of the liquids alone does not behave in a similar manner. However, this behaviour is not evident when one of the components in the mixture is less than 40%.

It may be further added that mixtures of *isoamyl* alcohol and *cyclohexane* or diphenyl oxide, when mixed in equal volumes, do not show the typical behaviour, while those with ethyl cyanoacetate or malonate do so. Mixtures of *isoamyl* alcohol containing 10% of palmitic and lauric acids, cetyl alcohol or citronellol show the same characteristic behaviour as that of the mixture of *isoamyl* alcohol and *isoamyl* acetate, indicating thereby the H-bond structure of fatty acids, alcohol or the constituent present in oil lemon.

The observations which need explanation are: (a) why liquids of the *isoamyl* alcohol group differ in their behaviour from those of the benzene group and (b) why those of the former group, when mixed in equal volumes, show the typical behaviour of amyl acetate, even though each separately does not behave in such a manner.

The liquids of the amyl alcohol group can form intermolecular complexes with amyl acetate involving the formation of H-bond between the hydroxy-, amino- or chloroform-H atom and the donor oxygen atom of the amyl acetate. Thereby, the proportion of molecular complexes, having H-bond structure, must be increasing to such an extent that it forms a sensitive interfacé, even when 10% of the ester is mixed with these liquids. The molecular interaction between the liquids of the benzene group and amyl acetate involving H-bond formation between the oxygen atom of the acetate and H-atom of these liquids is not possible and so their mixtures do not show the phenomenon, unless the ester is in excess. When the proportion of ester is not in excess in mixtures prepared with liquids of benzene group or is 5% in those of amyl alcohol group, the characteristic of H-bond structure is not evident, because the proportion of molecular complexes having H-bond must not be sufficient to build up an interface susceptible to electrical double layer reversal. When the liquids of the amyl alcohol group, viz. amyl alcohol, aniline, methylaniline or chloroform, are mixed with one another in equal proportion, the phenomenon characteristic of amyl acetate is observed as a result of intermolecular complex formation involving H-bond between the H-atom of one liquid molecule and the donor atom of the molecule of a different liquid. Such a complexing tendency is absent in liquids of the benzene group.

The authors thank the College Authorities for the facilities.